

BRONZA DAVRI HUNARMANDCHILIGI VA UNING AHAMIYATI

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Tarix ta'lim yo'nalishi talabasi.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bronza davrining vujudga kelishi va bu davrdan boshlab xo'jalikning turli sohasidagi bilimlar vujudga kelishi, manzillar hajmi yanada kengayganligi, aholi soni oshib borganligi (5 – 10 ming kishi). Bu tarixiy jarayon jamiyat taraqqiyotida dastlabki yirik mehnat taqsimoti bo'lib, ilk shaharlar paydo bo'lishi va rivojlanishiga zamin bo'ldi. Bronza davriga kelib O'rta Osiyoning janubiy hududlarida ilk dehqonchilik xo'jaligi tabiiy sug'roma dehqonchilik madaniyati qaror topdi. Bronza davri jamiyatining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va etno-madaniy rivojlanishining manbasi ekanligi haqida ma'lumotlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bronza, mis, qalay, enolit, dehqonchilik xo'jaligi, sug'orma dehqonchilik, dehqonchilik, chorvachilik, hunarmandchilik.

BRONZE AGE CRAFT AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE

Abstract. In this article, the emergence of the Bronze Age and the emergence of knowledge in various fields of economy from this period, the size of settlements expanded, and the population increased (5-10 thousand people). This historical process was the first large-scale division of labor in the development of society and became the basis for the emergence and development of the first cities.

By the Bronze Age, the first agricultural economy, the natural sugroma farming culture, settled in the southern regions of Central Asia. Information about the source of socio-economic and ethno-cultural development of the Bronze Age society is highlighted.

Key words: Bronze, copper, tin, enolith, agriculture, irrigated agriculture, farming, animal husbandry, crafts.

РЕМЕСЛО БРОНЗОВОГО ВЕКА И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье обсуждаются возникновение эпохи бронзы и появление знаний в различных областях экономики, размеры поселений, рост населения (5-10 тысяч человек). Этот исторический процесс явился первым масштабным разделением труда в развитии общества и стал основой возникновения и развития первых городов. К бронзовому веку в южных районах Средней Азии расселилось первое земледельческое хозяйство - естественная сугромная земледельческая культура. Освещены сведения об истоках социально-экономического и этнокультурного развития общества бронзового века.

Ключевые слова: Бронза, медь, олово, энолит, земледелие, орошаемое земледелие, земледелие, животноводство, ремесла.

Ma'lumki biz bilgan bronza Kichik Osiyo va Ikki daryo oralig'i deb ataluvchi Mesopotomiyada paydo bo'lgan. Bronzaning kashf etilishi juda katta va sezilarli darajada yangiliklarga sabab bo'ldi.

Aytish joizki, bronza eramizdan avvalgi 3-ming yillikda kashf etilgan. U mis bilan qalay qotishmasidan iborat bo'lib, nisbat jihatidan bronzaning tarkibi har xildir. Tarkibida 90% mis, 10%

qalay bo'lsa, eng yaxshi bronza hisoblanadi. paleolit, mezolit, neolit, Eneolit davrlaridan farqli ravishda bronza davri juda katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mesopotamiyada paydo bo'lganidan so'ng u orqali qo'shni hududlarga tarqaldi. Ammo, bu davr barcha yerda bir xil kechgan emas. Yevro Osiyoni olib qaraydigan bo'lsak, uning chekka-chekka hududlariga nisbatan kech yetib borgan. Ammo tosh butun bronza davri davomida ham metal bilan muvaffaqiyatli ravishda raqobat qilib, qurollar ishlash manbai sifatida o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan.

Mehnat qurollarini ishlab chiqarish uchun bronza kamchil metall bo'lib qolavergan.

Toshdan pichoqlar, o'roqlar, o'q va nayza uchlari ham yasalgan. Bronzaning paydo bo'lishi mis siqib chiqargan bo'lsada ammo toshni siqib chiqara olmadi.

Har davrda tosh o'z ahamiyatini uncha yo'qotmadi. Bronza qurollarini va xomashyolarini tayyorlashda albatta tosh ham kerak edi. Bu ikkala raqobatdosh metall hamda tosh insoniyatning mehnat unumdorligini oshirishga, atrof-muhit yer xo'jaligiga ham ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Bronza davriga xos moddiy-madaniy topilmalarni biz arxeologiya kabi sohalar orqali o'rganamiz.

Tadqiqotchilarimizning o'rganishlariga qaraganda bu davr ancha chuqur va boy tarixiy-madaniy topilmalar va madaniyatga ega deb e'tirof etiladi.

Eneolit davri-mis-tosh davridan bronza farq qiladi. Uning farqi shunda ediki, insonlar endilikda o'zlari uchun noyob, eng yaxshi samarali va kerakli madanga ega bo'lishgan. Bronza misga nisbatan juda pishiq, qulay hamda tarkibi jihatidan ancha farq qilar edi. Bronza tabiatda sof holda uchramas, uni mis va qalay qorishmasidan tayyorlashga insonlarning endi aqli ishlay boshladi. Bu o'z davrining yirik kashfiyotlaridan biri edi.

Bronzadan keyinchalik hunarmandchilikda foydalanila boshlandi. Metallardan ketmon, o'roq, tesha, bolta, xanjar, qilich, pichoq, nayza va shunga o'xshash buyumlar hamda zargarlik buyumlari yasala boshlandi. Bronza davrining muhim ixtirolaridan biri bu Omoch va G'ildirak, shu asosida arava yasalishi edi. Aravaning ixtiro etilishi insoniyat tarixida ilk bor hayvonlar transport sifatida foydalanila boshladi. Bu esa o'z navbatida savdo aloqalarini vujudga kelishiga zamin yaratgan. Bronza davrida maxsus hunarmandchilik ishlab chiqarish vujudga kelgan. O'rta Osiyoning turli viloyatlarida mutaxassis kulollar paydo bo'lgan. Mil.avv. 2-ming yillikda kulolchilik hunariga charx keng joriy etiladi.

Endilikda buning afzalligi kulollar ishini yanada tezlashtiribgina qolmay, sopol buyumlarning xilma-xil turlarini paydo bo'lishiga ham olib keldi. Bu davrga kelib dehqonchilik, chorvachilik, hunarmandchilik o'zining yuksak cho'qqilariga erishdi. Hunarmandchilikning kulolchilik sohasidagi yutuqlari sezilarli darajada insoniyatni yashash tarzini o'zgartira boshladi.

Endilikda odamlar o'zlariga ovqat pishirishlari uchun qozonlarni qo'lda yasay boshladilar. Sopol idishlarga naqshlar bilan ishlov berish, bo'yoqlardan foydalanish kishilarda madaniyat va did tushunchalarini uyg'ota boshladi.

Arxeologik qazishmalar chog'ida bronza davriga oid, shu metallardan yasalgan ayollarning turli-tuman taqinchoqlari endilikda ular o'zlarining tashqi ko'rinishiga ham e'tibor berayotganidan dalolat berardi. Bilamizki, bu davr hamma yerda hamma vaqtda bir xil kechgan emas. Xususan, O'rta Osiyoda ham. Janubiy O'zbekiston (Surxondaryo) o'troq aholining dastlabki markazlaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Ushbu viloyatda bronza davriga oid Sopollitepada to'rtburchakli istehkom qazib ochildi. Istehkom ichida turar joylar, ro'zg'or va xo'jalik xonalari, hunarmandchilik ustaxonalarining qoldiqlari topildi. Arxeologiya sohasida ham O'rta Osiyoda topilgan ko'pgina hunarmandchilik namunalari bronzaning o'z davrida nechog'lik katta ahamiyatga ega ekanligidan dalolat beradi.

Hunarmandchilik yakka o'zi rivojlanibgina qolmay u orqali savdo munosabatlari ham shakllandi. Mehnat taqsimotida dehqonchilikdan ajralib chiqqan hunarmandchilik xalqaro tovar almashishda sezilarli yutuqlarga erishdi.

Savdo-sotiqning rivojlanishiga nima sabab bo'ldi? degan savol tug'iladi. Bir tarzda rivojlanmayotgan insonlar guruhi va hududi boshqa hududlarda ancha hunarmandchilik sohasida ilgari ketgan odamlarning mehnat mahsuliga, zaruriy xomashyolarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj bu sohani rivojlanishiga turtki bo'ldi. Bu ijobiy o'zgarishlar ijtimoiy hayotga ham ta'sirini o'tkazmay qolmadi.

Tengsizlik va mulkiy tabaqalanish kuchaydi. Aholining bir-biriga bo'lgan qarshiligi ko'pgina muammoli vaziyatlarni vujudga keltirdi. Biz ko'rib turgan bu omillar davlatchilik shakllanishida muhim o'rin kasb etgan.

Tarix nazarida qaraydigan bo'lsak, bronzaning kashf etilishi, hududlarda keng tarqalishi, hunarmandchilik, dehqonchilik, savdo-sotiq munosabatlarida yangiliklar paydo bo'lishi insoniyatning ongi rivojlanishiga, aqliy faoliyati yanada o'sishiga hamda turmush tarzining o'zgarishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etgan. Ushbu davrda tasviriy san'at sohasini olib qaraydigan bo'lsak, madaniyatning ibtidoiy davrda qay darajada rivojlanganligini, ularning tafakkuri o'zgarishiga boshlaganini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ushbu davrda g'or va toshlarda chizilgan hayvonlar: tog' echkilari, kiyiklarni ovlash texnikasi, tabiiy hodisalarning topilganligi ibtidoiy odamlarda madaniyat tushunchasining asta-sekin rivojlanib borayotganligidan dalolat beradi.

Xullas, hozirgi kunga qadar to'plangan ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, bronzaning insoniyat tarixiga kirib kelishi, ongi rivojlantiribgina qolmay, butun turmush tarzida ham tub burilish yasay oldi, desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, metall ishlatishga o'tilishi qadimgi davrning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotini tezlashtirdi. Natijada O'rta Osiyo dasht va tog' oldi hududlariga chorvaga ega bo'lgan o'troq aholining bir qismi ko'chib borib joylashdi

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